

Ease of Transportation and Accommodation as Determinants of Tourism Patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Tourism has emerged as a major source of income for businesses and nations globally, acting as a key catalyst for both local and international economic development. It now ranks as the third largest export sector worldwide, following fuels and chemicals, and surpassing food and automotive products. This study examined the impact of transportation and accommodation accessibility on tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria. Specifically, it aimed to determine whether ease of transportation and the availability of quality accommodation serve as significant drivers of tourist visits within the state, located in Nigeria's South-East region. A descriptive research design was employed, targeting tourists who visited four major tourist destinations in the state. A sample size of 384 respondents was calculated using Cochran's formula, and primary data were collected through structured questionnaires. The data were analysed using frequency tables and percentages, while hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis at a 0.05 significance level. The results indicated that ease of transportation significantly influenced tourism patronage ($\beta = 0.309$, $p < 0.001$), as did accommodation ($\beta = 0.202$, $p < 0.006$). Based on these findings, the study recommends prioritising the improvement of transport infrastructure and accommodation standards to enhance tourist engagement in Anambra State, one of Nigeria's most economically vibrant regions. The outcomes hold important implications for policy reform aimed at revitalising the tourism industry in both the state and the country more broadly.

Keywords: *Ease of transportation, Accommodation, Tourism Patronage, Anambra State.*

JEL Classification codes: *O22, M12.*

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Introduction

Tourism has become a huge source of revenue generation to firms and nations around the world. According to the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2020), tourism is an important driver of economic growth both globally and locally. It has become the world's third-largest export industry after fuels and chemicals, and ahead of food and automotive products (Rasool *et al.*, 2021). Prior to the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic, international tourism witnessed an alarming growth and contributing significantly to national and global gross domestic products (GDP) annually (World Travel and Tourism Council, 2022; United Nations World Tourism Report, 2014). Undoubtedly, the sector remains a key creator of employment to a teeming population around the world. The immense contribution of tourism to revenue generation and job creation has been reported by the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) (2022) and Kosmas, & Vatikoti, (2024). Thus, prior to the covid-19 pandemic period, travel and tourism have significantly accounted for one fourth of the new jobs created across the world - 10.3% of all jobs (333 million), and 10.3% of global GDP (US\$9.6 trillion); international visitor spending amounted to US\$1.8 trillion (6.8%) of total exports in 2019 (WTTC, 2022).

Several fascinating tourist destinations and sites exist in Nigeria. These are found in different states of the federation. For instance, in Lagos State, there are the Elegushi Beach, Badagry Slave Post, National Museum and Lekki Conservation center; the Kajuru Castel, Nok Culture, and Kamuku National Park in Kaduna State, as well as Awhum Waterfall, Eze Agu Tourist Complex, Nike Resort in Enugu State, Igbo Ukwu Art gallery, Odinani Museum Agu-ukwu Nri in Anambra state among a host of others. Agu, Okereafor, Omotosho, Okocha, and Uche (2023) have pointed how religious organizations/activities have attracted local and international tourists to Nigerian states. For instance, Ikotun-Egbe in Lagos State, the location of T.B Joshua's Synagogue Church of All Nations, the Living Faith's Canaanland in Ota, Ogun State; RCCG - Redeemed Christian Church of God's Redemption Camp at Lagos-Ibadan Expressway; and Assemblies of God Church's Okpoto Campground in Ebonyi State; Catholic Holy Ghost Adoration Ministry Uke in Anambra state have remained religious tourist destinations in the country. Some of these amazing tourist attractions are already well known to the touring world, while others still at their developmental stages are largely unknown. Abubakar (2014) have earlier noted other numerous cultural, natural, and religious resources of tourism significance that are yet to be tapped.

Anambra State of reference is blessed with lots of tourist sites, but which are still largely developed, thus requiring the attention of government (Odogwu, 2022). Among the identified sites are Ogbunike Cave, and Waterfall, Agulu Lake, Iyiocha Lake, Odinani Museum Nri, Igbo Ukwu Art gallery. These sites, though active, have attained the expected level of tourist's visits required to contribute meaningfully to the economic growth of the state (Eyisi & Okonkwo, 2020).

Many studies have surreptitiously investigated determinants of tourism patronage in Nigeria. Onyeokoro and Agu (2021) highlighted the importance of factors such as accessible roads, security and sociocultural stereotypes. The importance of efficient transport system and comfortable accommodation has also been reported (Onyeokoro, 2022; Kong & Chang, 2016). However, insufficiency of research and available literature pertaining to Anambra State's exploration of innovative packaging, especially in the aspects of efficient transportation and accommodation, from a marketing viewpoint to attract customer patronage has sparked the interest of researchers. This study aimed to close this gap by determining the extent to which ease of transportation and accommodation influences tourism patronage in Anambra State.

Literature Review

Ease of Transportation

Transportation within Destination involves person getting from one place to another within a given destination - region, state, or municipality. Transportation around a destination entails not just the network of roads or pathways that are found within a tourist site but the ease with which tourists can navigate their ways around the site (Hussein, 2023; Adeleke & Ogunsusi, 2019). Ease of transportation, in the context of this study, involves movement of people and goods by land water, and air through their classified modes and variants, in their quest to patronise a tourist site (Nutsugbodo *et al.*, 2018). In the context of tourism destination, transportation refers to all the secured transportation that a tourist needs to reach his/her ultimate destination and visit to his/her desired site(s). Truong and Shimizu (2016) were unequivocal about the importance of transport to traveling to any place in the world, claiming that it is a major consideration for individuals wishing to visit places for business or recreation.

Getting around a destination is crucial for any traveler, whether they are exploring a new place or simply trying to navigate their own town. With so many transportation choices available, it can be challenging to plan the best way to get from one place to another. However, this can also lead to a memorable experience, especially if you are unfamiliar with the area. In light of this potential challenge, it is important for tourists to carefully consider the most effective means of transportation to navigate their destinations (Musa & Ndawayo, 2011).

Accommodation

As noted by Fletcher *et al.* (2017), finding optimal accommodation is one of the most important decisions in the tourists' journeys. Despite the availability of online websites and applications for booking accommodation, the issue is still complex due to the extensive number of available options in this sector and the numerous factors that affect the decision-making (Mahdi & Esztergar-Kiss, 2021).

Accommodation facilities vary in size and services, but their primary purpose is to provide customer service, where hotels, motels, guesthouses, and apartments are examples of places of accommodation (Suhaeni & Sosianik, 2018; Navratil *et al.*, 2012). Tourists choose the place according to their preferences and constraints, where cost, location, and services represent the basic elements of the consideration (Agbabiaka, 2022; Goeldner & Ritchie, 2007). Many studies examine the factors that affect the tourists' choices of accommodation. Psychological and non-psychological factors influence the decision-making process, especially in the field of tourism due to the variety and the competition among the alternatives (Mahdi & Esztergar-Kiss, 2020), as well as the potential need to escape from psychosocial turmoil that hinders optimal functioning (Ezeonwumelu *et al.*, 2021; Ezeonwumelu & Okoro, 2019). Losada *et al.* (2017) conducted a study on the types of accommodation chosen by senior tourists in Spain. An interview survey through telephone was used to obtain data on socio-demographic and self-perceived variables as well as factors linked to pull motivation. A multinomial logit model was applied to analyze the collected data. The study found that seven out of ten senior tourists preferred hotels.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the influence of destination packaging on tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. ascertain the extent to which ease of transportation influences tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria,
2. determine the level to which accommodation influences tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria,

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised from the specific objectives to guide the study:

1. To what extent does ease of transportation influence tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria?
2. To what level does accommodation influence tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses guided the study:

1. Ease of transportation has no influence on tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria.
2. Accommodation has no influence on tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Method

This study adopted the descriptive survey design in which case the questionnaire was used to obtain the primary data for the study. The area of the study is Anambra State in the South-East geo-political region of Nigeria. The name Anambra was derived from the Anambra River (Omambala) which flows through the area and is a tributary of the River Niger. Boundaries are formed by Enugu State to the East, Abia State to the South-East, Delta and Edo States to the West, Imo and Rivers States to the South, and Kogi State to the North. Anambra is the fourteenth-most populated state in the Federal Republic of Nigeria and the second most densely populated state in Nigeria after Lagos State (Top 10 most populated states in Nigeria, 2020). Anambra State is a destination in Nigeria home, to very attractive tourist sites. Ogbunike Caves, listed by UNESCO 2019 as a World Heritage Site, is one of the most visited tourist sites in Anambra State. It is classified as a sandstone cave. Largely unexplored, the caves are said to be the largest in West Africa. Igbo Ukwu Museum situate in Igbo-Ukwu is an ancient town known for its astonishing metal crafts; it continues to attract tourists to see its bronze artifacts. Other places of interest in the State include Catholic Holy Ghost Adoration Ministry located in Uke in Idemili-North LGA. Odinani Museum, Agu-ukwu Nri; located in Anaocha Local Government, houses lots of archaeological discoveries, cultural and traditional religious artifacts.

The target population of the study comprises the tourists (tourism destination patrons or users) in the chosen tourist centres under investigation namely Ogbunike Cave, Igbo-Ukwu Museum, Catholic Holy Ghost Adoration Ministry Uke, Odinani Museum, Agu-ukwu Nri. This target should be taken to be unknown/infinite given that they are 'active' in status – they come and go; to return next time or not just as new one's visit resulting in no steady record of the size of the population that can be relied on. Since the population size for the study is considered unknown, the sample size is determined using Cochran (1965) formula for determination of sample size for unknown population size. The sample size of 384 was equally distributed among the four centers, with 96 per center.

The researcher adopted the convenience sampling technique. The instrument for the study was a self-administered and structured questionnaire. in Likert scale of four points (strongly agree = 4, agree = 3, disagree = 2, and strongly disagree = 1). The research instrument was subjected to expert face, content, and constructs validation. The questionnaire was pretested in a pilot study to assess how reliable it was to generate the desired data. The pretest was conducted on twenty (20) Tourist drawn from Agulu Lake in Anaocha Local Government Area of Anambra State. The data collected from the study were thereafter analysed with Cronbach's alpha (α) to test the internal consistency of the variables. The technique for the analyses was percentages, frequency tables and multiple regressions.

Result

Table 1. Demographics Distribution of Participants of the Study

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	186	50.5
	Female	182	49.5
	Total	368	100
2	Age		
	18 – 30 years	130	35.3
	31 - 40 years	88	23.9
	41 – 50 years	78	21.2
	Above 50 years	72	19.6
	Total	368	100
3	Marital Status		
	Single	130	35.3
	Married	131	35.6
	Widow/widower	66	17.9
	Divorce/separated	41	11.1
	Total	368	100
4	Educational Level		
	No formal studies	85	23.1
	Primary	96	26.1
	Post primary	98	26.6
	Tertiary	89	24.2
	Total	368	100
5	Occupation		
	Public/civil servant	68	18.5
	Trading	123	33.4
	Self-employed	109	29.6
	Others	68	18.5
	Total	368	100
6	Income Per/month		
	Below N100,000	204	55.4
	N101,000-N200,000	80	21.7
	Above N200,000	84	22.8
	Total	368	100

Source: Computed from SPSS 26 Analysis

The demographic results of the tourists are presented based on the following: gender, age, marital status, educational level, occupation, and income level per month. The above Table 1 shows that 50.5% of tourism destination users who participated in this study were males and 49.5% were females. Thus, most tourists who participated in this study were males. This table reveals that most tourists (130) are within the age of 18 and 30 years old (35.3%). The table also shows that 88 tourists (23.9%) were aged between 31 and 40 years. The table indicates that 130 tourists (35.3%) are single, 131 (35.6%) are married, 66 (17.9%) are widow/widowed, and 41 (11.1%) are divorced or separated. This study thus clearly indicates that most of the tourism destination users are married. The tourism users were also queried as to their highest educational level attained. Results, as presented in Table 1, indicate that 85 tourists (23.1%) had no formal education. On the other hand, 96 of the tourists (26.1%) had attained primary school as their highest educational qualification. Again, 98 users of tourism destination (26.6%) have post-primary education as their highest educational qualification. The remaining 89 of them (24.2%) indicated that they had attained tertiary as their highest educational qualification. It is evident that 98 (26.6%) of the

tourism destination users had post-primary education as highest qualification. The results in Table 1 also show that tourism users who monthly earned below N100 000, were 204, or 55.4%, 80 representing 21.7% of the tourism users earned between N101 000 and N200 000 per month. This was similar to 84 (22.8%) tourists who earned above N200 000 per month. Following the assessment outcome, it evident that majority of tourists earned below N100 000 from the established business or public/civil service. The tourists were also queried regarding their occupation. The results are presented in Table 1 and reveal that 68 tourists (18.5%) of the are either public or civil servants. The results also show that 123 tourists (33.4%) are traders. It is notable that 109 of the tourism users (29.6%) are self-employed. The remaining 68 tourists (18.5%) are people in other professions. From the data, it is evident that majority of the tourists are either traders or self-employed.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Tourism Transportation

S/N	Tourism Transportation	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)
1	The availability of reliable transportation services is crucial in any tourist destinations Centre.	8 (2.2%)	2 (0.5%)	52 (14.1%)	306 (83.2%)
2	Inconvenient transportation within discourages me from visiting tourist destinations.	5 (1.4%)	5 (1.4%)	76 (20.7%)	282 (76.6%)
3	I consider transportation convenience as a significant factor when choosing tourist destinations within.	7 (1.9%)	4 (1.1%)	88 (23.9%)	269 (73.1%)
4	Poor transportation infrastructure significantly hinders my willingness to explore tourist spots.	10 (2.7%)	17 (4.6%)	101 (27.4%)	240 (65.2%)
5	I believe efficient transportation systems contribute to a positive overall tourist experience.	8 (2.2%)	28 (7.6%)	77 (20.9%)	255 (69.3%)

The results of the elements that constitute transportation reveal that 97.3% of the users of tourist destination agreed that they availability of reliable transportation services is crucial in any tourist destinations centre. while 97.3% of them believed that inconvenient transportation within discourages them from visiting tourist destinations. They (97%) also agreed that they consider transportation convenience as a significant factor when choosing tourist destinations within. It is note-worthy that 92.6% agreed that poor transportation infrastructure significantly hinders their willingness to explore tourist spots. Equally notable is that 90.2% of the users agreed that they believe efficient transportation systems contribute to a positive overall tourist experience.

Table 3. Frequency Distribution of Tourism Accommodation

S/N	Tourism Accommodation	Strongly Disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly Agree (4)
1	Uncomfortable accommodation options discourage me from visiting tourist destinations.	7 (1.9%)	23 (6.3%)	186 (50.5%)	152 (41.3%)
2	I prioritize comfortable and well-equipped accommodations when choosing to visit tourist attractions.	10 (2.7%)	47 (12.8%)	176 (47.8%)	135 (36.7%)
3	Accommodation is not a critical factor influencing my decision to explore tourist attractions.	10 (2.7%)	44 (12.0%)	195 (53.0%)	119 (32.3%)
4	A variety of accommodation choices enhances my overall satisfaction with tourist experiences.	18 (4.9%)	32 (8.7%)	98 (26.6%)	220 (59.8%)

5	I am willing to pay more for accommodation that meets high standards during my visits to tourist destinations.	27 (7.3%)	33 (9.0%)	92 (25.0%)	216 (58.7%)
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The result in Table 3 showed that 91.8% of the tourist destination user's uncomfortable accommodation options discourage them from visiting tourist destinations. The frequency distribution also shows that 84.5% of the users at least agreed that they prioritize comfortable and well-equipped accommodations when choosing to visit tourist attractions. Results show that accommodation is not a critical factor influencing their decision to explore tourist attractions, according to 85.3% of users who agreed. Furthermore, the users who at least agreed that variety of accommodation choices enhances tourist destination users' overall satisfaction with tourist experiences were 86.4%. The results further revealed that 83.7% of users at least agreed that they are willing to pay more for accommodation that meets high standards during their visits to tourist destinations.

Table 4. Frequency Distribution of Tourist Patronage

S/N	Tourist Patronage	Strongly disagree (1)	Disagree (2)	Agree (3)	Strongly agree (4)
1	Transportation within the destination centre influences my patronage of the destination centre.	2 (0.5%)	6 (1.6%)	98 (26.6%)	262 (71.2%)
2	Accommodation is a crucial factor that makes me to patronize tourist destinations centre.	---	19 (5.2%)	120 (32.6%)	229 (62.2%)

Table 4 depicts results regarding tourism patronage which comprised two elements. Results show that 2 (0.5%) and 6 (1.6%) users, respectively, strongly disagreed and disagreed that transportation within the destination centre influences their patronage of the destination centre. The users of tourist destination who agreed totalled 98 (26.6%) while 262 (71.2%) strongly agreed that transportation within the destination centre influences their patronage of the destination centre. 19 (5.2%) users disagreed that accommodation is a crucial factor that makes them to patronize tourist destinations centre. The users of tourist destination who agreed totalled 120 (32.6%) while the remaining 229 (62.2%) strongly agreed that accommodation is a crucial factor that makes them to patronize tourist destinations centre. The results showed that transportation within the destination centre influences their patronage of the destination centre, as agreed to by 97.8% of the users. In terms of tourism accommodation, 94.8% of the users maintained that accommodation is a crucial factor that makes them to patronize tourist destinations centre.

Table 5. Estimation Correlation Matrix

Correlations		Transportation	Accommodation	Tourist Patronage
Transportation	Pearson Correlation	1	.166**	.163**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.002
	N	368	368	368
Accommodation	Pearson Correlation	.166**	1	.177**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		<.001
	N	368	368	368
Tourist patronage	Pearson Correlation	.163**	.177**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	<.001	
	N	368	368	368

Table 5 above shows the correlational matrix of the variables used in this study. It is evident that there is a significant relationship between the variables.

Table 6. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.511 ^a	.262	.249	.587

a. Predictors: (Constant), transportation, accommodations

Table 6 shows the regression coefficient, 'R' has a value of 0.511, this indicate that 51.1 percent correlation between the dependent and independent variables, as seen in the model. Again, R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.262. This implies that 26.2% of the variation in tourism patronage in Anambra State, Nigeria are explained by variations in transportation, accommodations, this was supported by adjusted R² of (24.9).

Table 7. Coefficients ^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.389	.278		1.396	.000
	Transportation	.309	.066	.254	4.700	.001
	Accommodations	.202	.044	.003	.055	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Tourism patronage.

The regression model, as per Table 7, revealed that there is a significant influence between the independent variables of the elements of destination packaging (Transportation and Accommodations) and the dependent variable (tourism patronage). This shows that tourism packaging has a significant effect on the tourism patronage. Notably, the standardised Beta and the corresponding P-values for transportation ($\beta = 0.309$, $p < 0.001$), and accommodations ($\beta = 0.202$, $p < 0.006$), from the analysis, transportation made the largest contribution to the model. With these results in mind, one can say that transportation, and accommodations, jointly serve as a predictor of tourism patronage.

H₀₁: Ease of transportation has no influence on patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 7 revealed that the beta standardized coefficients ($\beta=0.309$) and with a P-value ($\text{sig}=0.001 < 0.05$). This implies that ease of transportation has significant influence on patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria. These results support the alternative hypothesis, which states that transportation has significant and positive influence on patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Accommodation has no influence on patronage of destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 7 also demonstrated a similar attribute, that is, the beta standardized coefficients ($\beta=0.202$) and with a P-value ($\text{sig}=0.006 < 0.05$). This shows that accommodation is significant on patronage of tourist destinations. These results support the alternative hypothesis, which states that

accommodation has significant and positive influence on patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria.

The Model of the Finding

Figure 1. Graphical presentation of contribution to knowledge

Source: Ezeoke's model 2024

Discussion of Findings

From the study, it was evident that majority of the tourist destination users revealed that the availability of reliable transportation services is crucial in any tourist destinations centre. They also believed that inconvenient transportation within discourages them from visiting tourist destinations. Majority of them asserts that they consider transportation convenience as a significant factor when choosing tourist destinations within. It is noteworthy that majority of the tourist destination users maintained that poor transportation infrastructure significantly hinders their willingness to explore tourist spots. Equally notable is that the users posit that they efficient transportation systems contribute to a positive overall tourist experience. Analysing further through a statistical tool, the study found that transportation has significant positive influence on patronage of destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria. This is in line with the findings of Adeleke and Ogunsusi (2019) that transportation accessibility between tourist destinations statistically influences tourists' visitation in Lagos, Nigeria. Similarly, Hussain (2023) findings revealed that air and railway transportation, including trade openness, positively affects inbound and outbound tourism in the long run in BRI countries. While Nutsugbodo *et al.* (2018) study found that generic dimensions of transport services, such as affordability, accessibility, availability, safety, and comfort, influenced the public transport mode choice of international tourists in Ghana.

From the study, it is clear that Most of the tourist destination users assert that uncomfortable accommodation options discourage them from visiting tourist destinations. The study further shows that majority of the users noted that they prioritize comfortable and well-equipped accommodations when choosing to visit tourist attractions. This points to show that accommodation is not a critical factor influencing their decision to explore tourist attractions, rather, the variety of accommodation choices enhance tourist destination users overall satisfaction with tourist experiences. The findings also revealed that most of the users assert that they are willing to pay more for accommodation that meets high standards during their visits to tourist destinations. Probing further to examine the level to which accommodation influences the patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria, the study found that accommodation has significant positive influence on the patronage of tourist destinations in Anambra State, Nigeria. This disagreed with the findings of Suhaeni and Sosianik (2018) that tourists tend not to be loyal to

budget accommodations because the service quality that they receive does not meet their expectations. However, the study supports the findings of Agbabiaka (2022) that tourists who had a positive experience with their accommodation were more likely to be satisfied with their overall trip and expressed a higher intention to revisit in the future. This underlines the importance of providing quality accommodation to enhance tourism patronage. Again, Udabor (2013) found that the quality and type of accommodation available in a destination significantly influence tourists' perception of the destination image. Udabor (2013) further posits that positive experiences with accommodation contribute to a favourable destination image, leading to increased tourism patronage. On the other hand, negative experiences with accommodation can tarnish the destination's reputation and discourage future visits. Therefore, accommodation plays a crucial role in the overall experience of tourists, as it directly affects their satisfaction and patronage. Abiola-Oke (2023) highlights the significance of various factors that influence tourists' choice of accommodation. These factors include location, price, facilities, and quality of service. Tourists are more likely to patronize accommodations that are conveniently located near tourist attractions, offer competitive prices, provide modern amenities, and deliver excellent customer service.

Conclusion

The study indicated that ease of transportation and accommodation have positively and significantly influence tourist visits, the study therefore concludes that destination packaging such as transportation and accommodation have positively impacts tourism patronage in Anambra State of Nigeria.

Recommendations

For the influence of destination packaging in attracting tourists to Anambra State, the following recommendations were proposed.

1. There should be a focus on improving transportation facilities. This includes upgrading existing roads, building new ones, and ensuring efficient public transportation systems. By providing ease of access to tourist destinations, more visitors will be inclined to explore the beauty of Anambra State.
2. The quality and variety of accommodation options need to be enhanced. This can be achieved by encouraging investment in hotels, resorts, and guesthouses that provide comfortable and affordable lodging. Additionally, efforts should be made to promote eco-friendly accommodations to attract environmentally conscious travelers.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study has made significant contributions to understanding of the factors that attract tourists to a destination. One major contribution of this study is the identification of the key elements of destination packaging that significantly influence tourism patronage. The findings suggest that providing convenient transportation options and a comfortable and well-maintained accommodation can greatly enhance the attractiveness of a tourist destination. This knowledge can be valuable for tourism stakeholders in Anambra State, as it provides them with insights into the specific aspects of destination packaging that they should focus on to attract more visitors.

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